

Supplementary Material for

Diversity patterns and speciation processes in a two-island system with continuous migration

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S1. SUPPLEMENTARY THEORY

A. One island dynamics without mating restrictions

To understand how the similarity between pairs of individuals changes through generations, we follow [1] and consider first an asexual population where each individual α has a single parent $P(\alpha)$ in the previous generation. The allele S_i^α will be equal to $S_i^{P(\alpha)}$ with probability $\frac{1}{2}(1 + e^{-2\mu})$ and $-S_i^{P(\alpha)}$ with probability $\frac{1}{2}(1 - e^{-2\mu})$, then the expected value is $E(S_i^\alpha) = e^{-2\mu} S_i^{P(\alpha)}$. For independent genes, the expected value of the similarity between α and β is, therefore,

$$E(q^{\alpha\beta}) = e^{-4\mu} q^{P(\alpha)P(\beta)}. \quad (1)$$

In sexual populations α and β have two parents each, $P_1(\alpha)$, $P_2(\alpha)$ and $P_1(\beta)$, $P_2(\beta)$. Since each one inherits (on average) half the alleles from each parent, we find

$$E(S_i^\alpha) = \frac{e^{-2\mu}}{2} (S_i^{P_1(\alpha)} + S_i^{P_2(\alpha)}). \quad (2)$$

Using the Eq. 1 of the main text, it follows that, on the average, the similarity between α and β is

$$q^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{e^{-4\mu}}{4} (q^{P_1(\alpha)P_1(\beta)} + q^{P_2(\alpha)P_1(\beta)} + q^{P_1(\alpha)P_2(\beta)} + q^{P_2(\alpha)P_2(\beta)}) \quad (3)$$

with $q^{\alpha\alpha} \equiv 1$. In the limit of infinitely many genes, $B \rightarrow \infty$, this expression becomes exact and the entire dynamics can be obtained by simply updating the similarity matrix.

The dynamics of the average similarity can be derived as follows: the probability that α and β have one parent in common is $4/M$ (the four possibilities are: $P_1(\alpha) = P_1(\beta)$, $P_1(\alpha) = P_2(\beta)$, $P_2(\alpha) = P_1(\beta)$ and $P_2(\alpha) = P_2(\beta)$). In this case, the average similarity between α and β would be (see Eq. 3)

$$\langle q^{\alpha\beta} \rangle = \frac{e^{-4\mu}}{4} (1 + 3q), \quad (4)$$

where q is the average similarity in the previous generation. If, on the other hand, α and β do not share a parent, which happens with probability $1 - 4/M$, then

$$\langle q^{\alpha\beta} \rangle = e^{-4\mu} q. \quad (5)$$

Therefore, at generation $t + 1$ we get

$$q_{t+1} = \frac{4}{M} \frac{e^{-4\mu}}{4} (1 + 3q_t) + \left(1 - \frac{4}{M}\right) e^{-4\mu} q_t \quad (6)$$

that simplifies to

$$q_{t+1} = e^{-4\mu} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{M}\right) q_t + \frac{1}{M} \right]. \quad (7)$$

Setting $q_{t+1} = q_t$ we find the equilibrium at

$$q_0 \approx \frac{1}{1 + 4\mu M}. \quad (8)$$

The approximation holds for μ and $1/M$ much smaller than one, which is always the case for real populations. Subtracting q_t from both sides of Eq. 7 and approximating $q_{t+1} - q_t = \dot{q}$, we get the differential equation

$$\dot{q} = \frac{1}{M} \left(1 - \frac{q}{q_0}\right) \quad (9)$$

whose solution is

$$q(t) = q_0 + (1 - q_0)e^{-t/Mq_0}. \quad (10)$$

When imposing the genetic restriction to mating, the time τ to sympatric speciation can be estimated as the time q takes to reach q_{min} . Setting $q(\tau) = q_{min}$ we find

$$\tau = Mq_0 \log \left(\frac{1 - q_0}{q_{min} - q_0} \right). \quad (11)$$

The population can also be characterized by the distribution of genetic distances $D^{\alpha\beta}$, defined as the number of loci bearing different alleles. It is easy to see that $q^{\alpha\beta} = 1 - 2D^{\alpha\beta}/B$. In this case mating is allowed only if the genomes differ by at most G loci, or $D^{\alpha\beta} \leq G$. The relation between G and q_{min} is given by

$$q_{min} = 1 - 2G/B. \quad (12)$$

In our simulations, we adopted $q_{min} = 0.9$, equivalent to $G/B = 0.05$.

B. Two islands dynamics

From the Eq. 3 of the main text, derived in [2], we obtain the dynamics of the similarities q and p . For ϵ , μ and $1/M$ all much smaller than 1, the equations can be approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} q_{t+1} &= (1 - 2\epsilon - 4\mu - M^{-1})q_t + M^{-1} + 2\epsilon p_t \\ p_{t+1} &= 2\epsilon q_t + (1 - 2\epsilon - 4\mu)p_t. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Using the approximations $q_{t+1} - q_t = \dot{q}$ and $p_{t+1} - p_t = \dot{p}$, we obtain the differential equations

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{q} &= -(2\epsilon + 4\mu + M^{-1})q + M^{-1} + 2\epsilon p \\ \dot{p} &= 2\epsilon q - (2\epsilon + 4\mu)p.\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

We obtain the solutions

$$q(t) = \left(a_1 - \frac{a_1}{\lambda_+} - \frac{2\sigma}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) e^{-\lambda_+ t/M} + 2\sigma \left(-a_2 + \frac{a_2}{\lambda_-} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) e^{-\lambda_- t/M} + q(0)\tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}p(t) &= \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{\Delta}}{4\sigma}\right) \left(a_1 - \frac{a_1}{\lambda_+} - \frac{2\sigma}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) e^{-\lambda_+ t/M} + \\ &\quad \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2}\right) \left(-a_2 + \frac{a_2}{\lambda_-} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Delta}}\right) e^{-\lambda_- t/M} + p(0)\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

where $q(0) = p(0) = 1$ and

$$a_1 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2\sqrt{\Delta}}, \quad a_2 = \frac{1 - \sqrt{\Delta}}{4\sigma\sqrt{\Delta}}, \quad \lambda_{\pm} = 2\sigma + \nu + \frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\Delta}, \quad \Delta = 16\sigma^2 + 1.\tag{17}$$

In the limit $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, the Eq. 10 for $q(t)$ is recovered, and $p(t)$ is simply given by $p(t) = e^{-\nu t/M}$. Considering two isolated islands without migration, the time for the speciation due to geographical isolation (τ_a) is approximated by $p(\tau_a) = e^{-\nu\tau_a/M} = q_{min}$. The time for allopatry can now be derived:

$$\tau_a = \frac{1}{4\mu} \log \frac{1}{q_{min}}.\tag{18}$$

C. Effective number of migrants

Here we calculate the number of migrants that effectively establish a sub-population in the arrival island, σ_{eff} . The probability that σ , of a total of M individuals, migrate to the other island is

$$P_M(\sigma) = \binom{M}{\sigma} \epsilon^\sigma (1 - \epsilon)^{M - \sigma}\tag{19}$$

where ϵ is migration probability per individual. These individuals will only give rise to a community if they reproduce and leave offspring to the next generation. For that, they have to be selected for reproduction (from the whole population M in M trials) and then select a mating partner among the migrants.

The probability of *not* selecting one among the σ migrants in one attempt is $1 - \sigma/M$. The probability of not selecting one among the σ migrants in M attempts is $(1 - \sigma/M)^M \approx e^{-\sigma}$.

Therefore the probability of selecting one migrant in M attempts is $(1 - e^{-\sigma})$. Similarly, the probability that the reproducing migrant selects another migrant as mating partner is $(1 - e^{-(\sigma-1)})$. Therefore, we can define an effective number of migrants (corresponding to successful migrants) as

$$\sigma_{eff} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{\sigma=2}^{m_k} \sigma P_{m_k}(\sigma) (1 - e^{-\sigma}) (1 - e^{-(\sigma-1)}) \quad (20)$$

where N is the number of species in the island where the migrants were born and m_k is the abundance of the k -th species. Because the migrants can belong to different species, we have constrained reproduction among individuals of the same species of migrants and averaged over all species. We can simplify this expression using the approximation that all species have the same number of individuals: $m = (q_{min}^{-1} - 1)/4\mu$ and $N = M/m$. We obtain

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sum_{\sigma=2}^m \sigma \binom{m}{\sigma} \epsilon^\sigma (1 - \epsilon)^{m-\sigma} (1 - e^{-\sigma}) (1 - e^{-(\sigma-1)}). \quad (21)$$

If the probability $P_m(\sigma)$ is peaked on the average value $\bar{\sigma} = M\epsilon$, we can further approximate this expression by

$$\sigma_{eff} = \bar{\sigma} (1 - e^{-\bar{\sigma}}) (1 - e^{-(\bar{\sigma}-1)}) \quad (22)$$

which recovers $\sigma_{eff} = \bar{\sigma}$ for $\bar{\sigma} \gg 1$. We considered the effective number of migrants for the calculations of the expected number of species N and N_T (Fig. 3 a and b in the main text).

S2. SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

A. Number of simulations

Figure S1 shows the number of simulations performed for each genome size, population size, and migration probability to compose Figure 2 of the main text. For parameter values resulting in a small number of species (≈ 1), we could make fewer simulations to calculate the average value since fluctuations were small. This was convenient for simulations of finite genomes that demand high computational time. Notice that few realizations are sufficient above the migration intensity for which the number of species collapses to a single one shared. For the analysis with fixed population size $M = 200$ (Fig. 3 and 4 of the main text), we ran 50 simulations in all cases.

Figure S1. Number of simulations (color scale) performed to compose Figure 2 of the main text.

B. Evolution of diversity for $B = 1000$, 2000 , and 3000

Here we present additional results to support our analysis in the manuscript. Figures S2, S3 and S4 show the patterns of diversity for the genome sizes $B = 1000$, 2000 , and 3000 respectively, similarly to Figure 2 in the main text, in different time steps: $T = 500$, 1500 and 2000 generations. In each figure, the columns represent the time of the observation. From top to bottom, the plots represent the average values of the total number of species in the insular system (N_T), the number of species per island ($\bar{N} = (N_1 + N_2)/2$), the ratio of the total number of species that are exclusive to an island (β_I), the number of ring-like

species (N_{ring}), and the asymmetry in species richness ($\Delta N = |N_1 - N_2|/\bar{N}$). The numbers of simulations utilized follow the indicated in Figure S1. The diversity patterns were consistent over time, but larger populations took longer to speciate in allopatry or with migration, i.e., the time to speciation depends on M for finite genomes.

Figure S5 depicts the dynamics in the two islands for some values of migration probability and fixed population size $M = 200$. The colors identify species, and the height is proportional to the species abundance. In allopatry ($\epsilon = 0$), we observe that sympatric speciation occurred only for $B = 3000$. Also, differentiation between islands took longer the shorter the genome size. Migration induced speciation up to a critical value of ϵ that collapsed the populations to a single shared species. Longer genomes supported higher migration flux before collapsing.

Figure S2. Diversity patterns of the two-island system as a function of population size (M) and migration probability (ϵ) for $B = 1000$ at $T = 500$ (left column), 1000 (middle) and 2000 (right column) generations.

Figure S3. Diversity patterns of the two-island system as a function of population size (M) and migration probability (ϵ) for $B = 2000$ at $T = 500$ (left column), 1000 (middle) and 2000 (right column) generations.

Figure S4. Diversity patterns of the two-island system as a function of population size (M) and migration probability (ϵ) for $B = 3000$ at $T = 500$ (left column), 1000 (middle) and 2000 (right column) generations.

Figure S5. Distribution of species per island over time for different migration probabilities (indicated in each panel) and fixed population size $M = 200$, for $B = 1000$ (left column), 2000 (middle) and 3000 (left column). Each panel has two horizontal bars corresponding to each island. The colors identify species, and their vertical amplitude represents the species abundance. The horizontal black line between the bars indicates the intervals when the islands shared at least one common species.

C. Number of exclusive species

Figure S6 depicts the number of exclusive (endemic) species in the insular system for varied genome sizes, complimentary to Figures 3 and 4 of the main text. The number of exclusive species in each island can be calculated as follows: calling K_i the number of endemic species to the island i and c the number of common species, then $N_1 = K_1 + c$, $N_2 = K_2 + c$, and $N_T = K_1 + K_2 + c$. Then $c = N_1 + N_2 - N_T$, and K_1 and K_2 are trivially calculated. The beta diversity index is given by the ratio $(K_1 + K_2)/N_T$.

Figure S6. Number of exclusive species in the system, $K_1 + K_2$.

D. Trade-off between genome length (B), minimal similarity for reproduction (q_{min}), mutation rate (μ) and population size (M)

In general, by decreasing the minimal genetic similarity for reproduction q_{min} , the total number of species decreases, following the trend of the number of species per island, N (Eq. 5 of the main text). Figure S7a shows that the qualitative patterns obtained when B increases while keeping the other parameters fixed (Fig. 3b) can be recovered by decreasing q_{min} . A similar scaling of effects occurs for the mutation rate: the patterns obtained by decreasing B (Fig. 3b) are recovered by decreasing the mutation rate (Fig. S7b).

Furthermore, we expect the observed effects to scale with genome length and population size, as shown in Figure 2. In Figure S8, we choose sets of B and M from the map in Figure 2 that demonstrates the similar behavior of the total number of species with the migration rate

(here plotted as a function of the number of migrants for convenience), i.e., the increase in richness when there are few migrants, followed by the collapse to a single shared species for a high migration intensity. Therefore, although we were limited to simulating small population sizes and genome lengths due to the computational time, we expect similar effects for larger populations with larger values B .

Figure S7. Effect of the minimal genetic similarity q_{min} (a) and mutation rate μ (b) on the total species richness. The other simulation parameters, unless varied in the graph, were: $B = 3000$, $M = 200$, $\mu = 0.001$, and $q_{min} = 0.9$.

Figure S8. Selected sets of B and M from Figure 2 of the main text showing the behavior of N_T with the number of migrants.

E. Null test of asymmetry

The asymmetry in species richness, calculated by the absolute value of the difference between the number of species in each island, $|N_1 - N_2|$, is equivalent to the modulus of the difference between the number of exclusive (endemic) species, $|K_1 - K_2|$. To verify if the asymmetry observed in our simulations was significant, we compared it to a null model where the exclusive species were randomly distributed between the islands with equal probability. We run the null model for each simulation output using the number of exclusive species from the simulation. In each case, we ensured that at least one species inhabited each island: if the islands shared at least one species, $K_1 + K_2$ species were randomly distributed between the islands, otherwise only $K_1 + K_2 - 2$ species were distributed, since one species is placed at each island at the start. To compare the different genome sizes, we adopted the asymmetry normalized by the total number of species, ΔN (Eq. 7 in the main text).

Figure S9 shows that the simulations differed from the random distribution when the migration probability was low ($\epsilon < 0.03$). For small genomes ($B = 1000$ and 2000), the asymmetry was higher than expected by chance, while for large genomes ($B = 3000$ and 10000), it was lower than the expectation at random. The higher asymmetry for small genomes suggests that speciation by founding populations was probably the main speciation mechanism associated: random imbalances in N_1 and N_2 were enhanced because migrants leaving the island with lower richness were more likely to be genetically compatible and to found a new species in the arrival island. On the other hand, the number of species was higher for larger genomes, decreasing the fluctuations in species richness and the likelihood of founding populations.

The divergence between the simulations and the null model is better observed in Figure S10, which compares the difference $N_1 - N_2$ (here is not the absolute value) for 1000 realizations with $\epsilon = 0.01$ and two values of genome size, $B = 2000$ (left) and 3000 (right). The distribution of $N_1 - N_2$ when $B = 2000$ has a plateau for $|N_1 - N_2| \leq 3$ (blue bars), revealing that perfect symmetry ($N_1 - N_2 = 0$) is not more likely within this range, in opposite to what is expected by chance (red bars). On the other hand, the distribution of $N_1 - N_2$ for $B = 3000$ (right, blue bars) is narrower than expected by chance (red bars), then perfect symmetry is more likely to occur.

Figure S9. Asymmetry in species richness in the insular system (ΔN) for finite genomes. The solid lines represent the average value of all simulations, and the shadowed areas show a confidence interval of 90%. (a) Results from our simulations (similar to the plot in the manuscript (Fig. 3c) considering only finite genomes and more data (some averages were calculated over 1000 repetitions). (b) Species asymmetry expected by the null model, where species are randomly distributed over the islands. (c) Comparison between the obtained from simulation and null model ($\Delta N - \Delta N_{null}$) reveals that asymmetry is more expected than by chance (positive values) for low migration probability and small genomes, $B = 1000$ and 2000 . The dashed vertical line highlight $\epsilon = 0.01$ (same as Fig. S10).

Figure S10. Histograms of the difference between the islands species richness, $N_1 - N_2$, obtained from the simulations (blue) and the null model (red) for 1000 replications when the migration probability is $\epsilon = 0.01$. For $B = 2000$ (left), the asymmetry is higher than expected by chance, while for $B = 3000$ (right) the asymmetry is lower than expected by chance.

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